

CarE-Service

**Circular economy business models
for innovative hybrid and electric mobility through
advanced reuse and remanufacturing technologies and services**

Risk management and identification of side-effects

(Deliverable 2.3)

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is the work performed under CarE-Service WP2 “New circular economy business models and service engineering” and reports outcomes of Task 2.3 “Risk management and identification of side-effects”. It consists, for each business model identified in previous activities (T2.1 and T2.2) in the systematic characterization of the drawbacks of the proposed business models and services (i.e. the decrease of revenues from sales of new vehicles and parts due to the increase of re-use practices, the environmental impact generated in the new re-use value chains, etc.). A comprehensive logical framework of interlinked variables has been built in order to have a complete systematic view on the identified drawbacks and, on the other side, on the positive impacts of the realized innovations that can compensate their effect.

The major business model identified during T2.1 and T2.2 was the new EV car sharing model linked with other transportation mode, the battery reuse, the metal part remanufacturing and the techno-polymer recycling. The major side effects of the project could be summarized as follow: less business for

- OEM: less car sold,
- Battery pack suppliers and all the battery supply chain (Battery reuse decrease the need of new batteries),
- Metal part suppliers and metal works, but on a long-term basis, as the quality of remanufacturing product decrease, the impact is limited
- Techno polymer raw material suppliers; on a long-term basis the impact could be huge as the techno-polymer could be recycled without any lost in performances forever.

On the other hand, circular economy in the EV car sharing services will bring major positive impacts:

- Environmental: less CO₂ consumption thanks to EV but also thanks to less battery production and metal part remanufacturing,
- Global cost decrease at all the level of the value-chain: 2nd life battery, remanufacturing metal parts and recycled techno-polymer will be cheaper; EV made with those recycled and remanufactured products will be cheaper,
- Creation of new business: battery pack dismantling, testing and remanufacturing, metal part remanufacturing, techno-polymer recycling, additional business for car dismantler, new logistical business and model thanks to the ICT Platform and the Smart Mobile Modules.

This Task provides inputs for the development of economic models that can be used for the assessment of socio-economic impacts of new circular business models in T2.4: “Socio-economic simulation of new services and business models”.

List of Acronyms

B2B:	Business to business
B2C:	Business to Consumer
BM:	Business Model
CA:	Consortium agreement
CC:	Consumer Committee
EC:	European Commission
EV:	Electric vehicle
GA:	General Assembly
GA:	Grant agreement
IB:	Innovation Board
ICT:	Information and Communication Technology
IPR:	Intellectual Property Right
NDA:	Non-disclosure agreement
PC:	Project Coordinator
PM:	Project Manager
QAP:	Quality Assurance Plan
RD:	Dissemination/Exploitation Risk
RI:	Implementation/Validation Risk
RO:	Organisational Risk
RT:	Technological Risk
SC:	Steering Committee
SG:	Stakeholders’ Group
WP:	Work Package

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1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of this deliverable is to analyse the side-effects and drawbacks emerging from new circular business models and mobility services identified in previous project activities (Task 2.1 Task 2.2). Side effects and drawbacks identify the negative consequences potentially introduced by the new business models and services.

With this goal, a logical framework of interlinked variables positively and negatively affecting the performance of new business models and mobility services was elaborated in the B2B circular scenarios of Batteries, Metals, techno-polymers, as well as in the B2C scenario of new mobility services. The systematic identification of those variables allows to include in the overall assessment of new business models and mobility services not only their benefits, which are the driving reason of the proposed circular economy approach on electric vehicles, but also their negative consequences, which might undermine their success. Furthermore, this approach allows to consider interlinks among positive and negative variables, that are often neglected when taking a specific technological assessment perspective.

2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology for the identification of drawbacks and side effects consisted of the following steps:

1) First identification of drawbacks and side effects by a restricted group of partners, that combined their multi-disciplinary knowledge to identify drawbacks. In particular, the activity was led by the partner Avicenne that, by operating as a consulting company in the global market of batteries, could provide its wide business and marketing intelligence knowledge. CNR contributed in this phase by proposing and introducing a model to exhaustively identify and represent interlinked variables. The model consisted of two main instruments:

- Tables for the systematic identification of pros and cons of each business scenario for all involved actors: involved actors in the value chain was the result of D2.1 for B2B business models and D2.2 for B2C business models. Taking an organizational view, the compilation of such tables requires the systematic and exhaustive analysis of the effects of circular business models and mobility services. Thus, it supports the identification of all positive and negative consequences of business models and mobility services;
- Maps of interlinked variables for each industrial scenario, i.e. maps for the representation of variables determining drawbacks and of their interrelations. Variables in the maps can be identified considering the pros and cons that emerged in the previous tables.

In this first phase of the task, tables and maps were built for the B2B and B2C project scenarios, i.e. the establishment of circular economy practices in the batteries, metals and techno polymers recovery streams, as the offering of innovative mobility services.

2) The initial proposal of tables and maps was improved and validated including the wider perspective of OEMs, companies in the recycling and remanufacturing chains, ICT platforms specialists and logistics providers, in a validation workshop that was organized in the frame of a project General Assembly (Madrid, 28-30/10/2019). In such a workshop, project partners representing those perspectives were split in four groups and were requested to comment, improve and validate the initial proposal. Results of the workshop were used to enlarge the initial framework and to finalise the maps of drawbacks and side effects.

In the next chapter results are presented for each addressed business scenario.

3 RESULTS: Drawbacks and side effects

Drawbacks and side effects were analysed for the four main business scenarios addressed in the project: the offering of innovative mobility services and the establishment of new business models in the battery, metals and techno-polymers recovery chains from electric vehicles.

3.1 Drawbacks and side-effects of B2C-Mobility Services

The new shared mobility services will generate positive impacts for **consumer** in terms of reduction of mobility costs and “easy of transportation” due to the integration of all transportation means and non-ownership model. However, vehicle non-ownership may constitute a drawback for some customers, since owning a car is still something that many customers prefer. In addition, in general, sharing models’ risk to limit the “mobility freedom”, i.e. the possibility to move at any time without planning the trip.

Considering **automotive OEMs**, increase of sharing transportation would reduce the sales of cars to private individuals, which is now the main market of car manufacturers. On the other hand, sales of cars to sharing/renting/fleet companies will increase due to their increased activity. In addition, it can be expected that customers in this revenue stream will renovate their vehicles more frequently compared to private citizens, due to their need to offer customers up-to-date vehicles.

From the **car sharing/renting companies’** perspective, the diffusion of new mobility services in Europe will have the positive effect to increase their market and turnover, due to the higher number of customers that will be served. In addition, according to the CarE-Service goals, the value-added of the provided services will increase, generating new reasons for strategic differentiation from competitors and new sources for potential additional profits. However, as a side effect, a higher competition will be faced not only in the direct market, but also in the use of available resources and infrastructure needed for operations of electric vehicles (charging stations, energy, maintenance, etc.). Furthermore, the complexity of the business will considerably increase due to the new circular economy paradigm in fleets management and to the integration of sharing/renting services into wider integrated service models including other transportation means (Train, e-bikes, subway, airports).

Taking the perspective of End-Of-Life actors, **remanufacturers** will mainly face advantages from the establishment of circular economy-based mobility services. In fact, the introduction of re-used/remanufactured parts in vehicles as a standard fleets management paradigm will generate significant market increase for them. However, increased market and the CarE-Service platform will generate new competition from companies that will enter this sector. Market will increase also from **recyclers’** point of view. In addition, the latter could establish more solid partnerships with OEMs in order to include recycled materials into fleets vehicles (and new vehicles in general). However, for recyclers, drawbacks could be faced as a consequence of the wider re-use/remanufacturing approach, that will prolong the usage of parts before they are recycled. Consequently, parts quality at the recycling time will be lower and their value reduced. Furthermore, the availability of recyclable parts will be postponed in time, due to longer use cycles.

Considering the **suppliers of new parts for electric vehicles** (batteries, metals and techno-polymers), an evident side-effect of the new business models will be the increased competition of re-manufactured/re-used parts: the increased future availability of such parts will offer customers the option to choose between new and non-new (cheaper) parts, with a consequent market reduction for the first ones. However, on the other hand, producers of new parts could evaluate the opportunity to adapt their business to the re-use/remanufacturing market, i.e. producing new parts with higher re-

use/remanufacturing potential and even entering themselves in the new market (becoming producers of new parts and remanufacturers at the same time).

Dismantlers will potentially increase their business because of the systematic disassembly and management of high value-added parts of electric vehicles, that at the moment they do not handle and are not ready to treat. On the other hand, they will have to acquire knowledge on the new electric vehicles products and will have to modify their sites in order to host disassembly operations that imply particular attention to safety and ergonomics.

Finally, **maintenance companies** will benefit from the establishment of the envisaged circular economy paradigm, since this will imply that vehicles will potentially need more maintenance/upgrade services. In fact, such a service (prolonging vehicles use life through periodic remanufacturing and upgrade operations) could represent a new value proposition per se which could potentially differentiate automotive service providers and increase their market. On the other side, they will have to invest in order to introduce new technologies and processes to offer structured and efficient maintenance/upgrade services for electric vehicles, which represent in fact a new product of higher complexity and with higher safety standards. Indeed, in case maintenance is provided by OEMs, the reduction of sales of new vehicles could be compensated by the increase of maintenance/upgrade activities.

Main pros and cons for actors of the re-use chains (B2C)

Actors	Pros	Cons (Side effects)
Consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced mobility cost No vehicle ownership burden 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Losing vehicle ownership Reduction of mobility freedom
OEM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase sales for fleets (B2B) Higher cars substitution rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced sales to private individuals (B2C)
Car sharing companies & Fleet management companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More customers and market increase Higher added value of provided services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More competition as the number of car-sharing companies increase More competition in the use of resources Increased business complexity
Remanufacturers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased market for remanufactured parts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher competition of newcomers in the remanufacturing business
Recyclers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased market for recycled materials Higher integration with OEMs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lower value of recycled parts Postponement in time availability of recyclable parts
New part's providers (Battery, metal and techno-polymer)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potential integration with remanufacturing/recycling businesses Higher value of new parts in order to be remanufactured/recycled 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Competition with remanufactured parts
Dismantlers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New knowledge and investments to manage disassembly of electric vehicles
Maintenance companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New market and business opportunities thanks to circular economy of electric vehicles Differentiation from traditional maintenance providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New processes and technologies (investments) for maintenance/upgrade of electric vehicles

Table 1. Main pros and cons for actors of the re-use chains (B2C)

In addition to the positive and negative impacts for the various stakeholders, the new mobility services and circular economy business models will have impacts on the environment and sustainability. For example:

- The diffusion of electric car sharing will increase environmental sustainability due to lower emissions and lower number of circulating vehicles (because of higher saturation). However, on the other side, it will require more energy to be produced.
- Circular economy of electric vehicles will reduce negative environmental impact thanks to re-use, remanufacturing and recycling but, on the other hands, remanufacturing, recycling and reverse logistics processes will generate themselves an environmental impact.
- Then, as a side effect, taxes collected by the government on gasoline will decrease.

Combining all this information, the map of side effects of new mobility services and circular business models is proposed in Fig.1.

Figure 1. New car sharing with EVs and services Side effect map

3.2 Side effect and positive impact by actors for Battery Reuse

The table below shows the contributed results from consortium partners in the 4th General Assembly meeting, with careful analysis of the drawbacks from Re-using of batteries regarding the main market players.

Battery re-use could mean different business models:

- Battery pack re-use directly in a new application, typically, stationary application where energy density is not so important than in the EV business.
- Battery pack and module dismantle, then test the cell, the module, the pack and make a new pack with old module or old cells.
- Battery pack reuse directly in a car: some cars may need to have a full capacity battery to get high range but some other cars, used by short-distance driver may need less energy and the old battery could be enough.

In this regard, the table below will provide a study of possible drawbacks for each player actors impacted by the Battery re-use in general and for the different business model. On a second step, in the V2 document (Month 24 – May 2020), we will need to detail those side effect for selected business model.

The main side effect of battery reuse, but also battery recycling is the business decrease for all the battery supply chain: **Battery suppliers** will sale less product. That mean that **raw material extractors**, **component producers** (cathode, anode, electrolyte, separators), **cell producers**, will all loose business. On the other hand, pack producer will be less dependent on cell supply chain located mostly in Asia. Cell suppliers and component suppliers will be less dependent on raw material suppliers and recycling or reuse batteries is a way to secure the supply chain. Cobalt is mainly extract in Congo Lithium is coming from South America. Both part of the world where the business is not easy and with additional issues for a country like Congo where cobalt could be extract by hand and by children. Then, reuse of battery will reduce CO2 emission coming from battery manufacturing, component manufacturing and raw material extraction.

As always, for the **customer** perspective economically brings more benefit comparing new battery at the final cost of purchasing, whilst technically durability of charging and discharging rate of the batteries are still doubtful. The customer could be a completely new application (stationary application, e-bikes) or the same application.

For **OEM** side effect are not clearly identified today as the legislation is not yet known. Depending on the legislation, OEM could have to warranty the old battery and may be responsible in case of accident when used in a new application. Again, depending on the future legislation the OEM will may be not in charge of recycling anymore.

For Fleet management and car sharing, they could be responsible of the battery during the second life and depending on the legislation may have to manage this. In the other hand they will make money from there old batteries.

In the case of re-use the battery in the same application, the price of reused parts is lower, but the lifetime and the range of the car will be lower also.

For **remanufacturers**, the re-use of battery is clearly a positive impact as they will have more business to dismantle the pack, test the elements and repack the battery. On the other hand, as it is clearly a new business, we will see an increase of the competition due to new remanufacturers entering the

market that could be, specialist in batteries, pack dismantlers, OEM, battery testing companies. Today there are clearly multiple business model possible depending on the level of vertical integration. Because of battery re-use in a 2nd life, **Recyclers** business will be postponed. Logistic providers will have to face with higher risk for storage and transportation of old batteries. On the other hand, they will have more business due to increase transportation needs of reverse logistics. **The logistical network** (storage, transportation) will have to manage more dangerous product as an old battery is less safe than a new one. Old battery transport and storage will be more expensive. On the other hand, more business will be generated due to increase transportation needs of reverse logistics.

Main actors' side-effects table for Reusing Battery(B2B)

Actors	Pros	Cons (Side effects)
Raw material extractors		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less business due to both battery recycling and battery re-use
Cell component suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less dependence on the rare materials: Cobalt, Lithium... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less business due to both battery recycling and battery re-use
Cell suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less dependence on the cell component supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less business due to both battery recycling and battery re-use
Battery pack suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less dependence on cell supply chain located mostly in Asia today 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less business due to both battery recycling and battery re-use
Customers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lower price of battery Less dependence on the battery supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Life time of the battery
OEM (Car Manufacturer)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depending on the future legislation the OEM will may be not in charge of recycling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manage the proper warranty of the old battery
Fleet management companies (B2B)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sales of old batteries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Could be responsible of the old battery during the 2nd life
Car sharing companies (B2C)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sales of old batteries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Could be responsible of the old battery during the 2nd life
Remanufacturers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New business: cell, module and pack test and re-packed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Competition of new remanufacturing companies entering the market Investment have to be made to enter the business
Recyclers		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Postpone battery availability for recycling
Logistics providers carriers & transporters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More business due to increase transportation needs of reverse logistics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More risk related to transport and storage of old batteries
Car Dismantlers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More business if they manage the battery dismantling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invest to create specific areas for batteries dismantling

Table 2. Main actors' side-effects table for Reusing Battery(B2B)

3.3 Side effect and positive impact by actors for Metal parts (Remanufacturing)

The table below is showing the contributed results from consortium partners in the 4th General Assembly meeting, with carefully analysing the drawbacks from Re-use/manufacture of metal on the main market players.

First, **new part supplier, steel works** and will lose business. In the other hand, the new part supplier may be involved in the metal part remanufacturing. **Metal raw material supplier** are Not really impacted because metal part that are not reused are send for recycling today.

For **OEM & car workshop** which are the main target of re-designed concept, there will be an increase of product portfolio with the aim of new Circular Vehicle design with possibility of upgrading and maintaining the parts. In addition, there will be a fulfilment of CO2 reduction regulation on manufacturing the vehicles with using reused and remanufactured parts for OEM. OEM & car workshop will probably get remanufactured metal part at lower cost than new parts, but they will have to deal with less quality.

The **consumer** may perceive vehicles with lower quality compared to original ones. But, the consumer could also benefit indirectly from lower service price offered by the car sharing services thanks to lower car cost.

Car sharing companies and fleet management will receive benefits with less expensive car.

From **Remanufacturing** point of view, this type of businesses will be a totally new opportunity to increase their market share and profits: At the moment there is no company doing reforming of automotive parts for cars so it will be a completely new business may be taken by new players or by car dismantler. However, those players making remanufacturer metal part will have to manage carefully the quality of the metal parts.

For **Recyclers**, they will have to wait longer some metal parts and part of the business will be postponed.

Logistics and carriers' businesses will grow due to B2B communication Platform among the parts providers and suppliers and the market demands in order to transport parts to the requested destination.

This redesign concept will cause a market loss for the new parts provider in the market rather than any possible stakeholders and actors, with less revenue due to Circular parts acquisition strategy.

On the other hand, a new business that do not exist today will grow. The remanufacturing metal parts in the car will be done by new entrants or existing players like car dismantlers or metal parts suppliers. dismantlers and generally the marketplace will have a benefit with adopting new strategy into their existing business models and more opportunity to have a bigger market share. In addition, the governments also will receive social and environmental benefits regarding less raw material consumption and less emission.

Main actors' side-effects table for Metal parts (B2B)

Actors	Pros	Cons (Side effects)
New parts providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Could enter the remanufacturing metal parts business 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less revenues, new competitors
Raw material suppliers		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not really impacted because metal part that are not reused are send for recycling today
Steel works		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less revenues
OEM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the product portfolio: New car/Vehicles with Circular Economy purpose • Reduce the metal part cost • Fulfillment of future regulations for re-manufacturing and reduce of CO2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parts with lower value and lower quality •
Consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May benefit to have lower price services thanks to lower cost car paid by the fleet management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceive less quality cars
Car workshop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower cost of the remanufactured metal part 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have to manage the quality of the remanufacturer part
Car sharing companies & Fleet management companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the upgrade of cars through remanufactured metals will Reduce the cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceive less quality cars
Remanufacturers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completely new business 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Must manage the quality of the remanufacturer part
Recyclers		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less revenues or at least postponed of the business
Logistics providers carriers & transporters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More business due to increase transportation needs of reverse logistics 	
Dismantlers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No change, if they NOT go into the re-manufacturing market 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	

Table 3. Main actors' side-effects table for Metal parts (B2B)

3.4 Side effect and positive impact by actors for Techno-polymer recycling

Currently techno-polymers are recycled for post-industrial use. The aspect we would like to explore and add to this value chain is recycling of techno-polymer parts for post-consumer use. The novelty we would like to contribute to this value chain is the possibility to create linkages between various stakeholders in the value chain in order to improve their efficiency and guarantee long term viability. Presently, car dismantlers do not recycle techno-polymer parts for the automotive value chain, rather they sell them as spare parts or throw them away as waste. With new partnerships, there may be possibilities to create value in more ways such as through recycling of techno-polymer parts that have previously been considered waste. Remanufacturing processes are not yet possible in the techno-polymer value chain since it is not possible to rework on plastics that have been damaged.

For this techno polymer recycling Business Model, the following side effects are analysed based on the table of stakeholder's effects.

The first side effect is the loss of revenues of **Raw material suppliers**. Year after year, recycled polymer will increase and impact directly the raw material suppliers' sales. As polymer can be recycled forever with the same final quality, we can imagine on a very long term that raw material supplier activity almost disappears.

Then, **Tier one supplier** will have to deal with lower cost raw material coming from recycling. It could be good for their margin and increase the product portfolio but it will also add competition between product coming from new raw materials and recycled raw materials.

OEM and car workshop will increase the product portfolio: new car/Vehicles with Circular Economy purpose. Then OEM could expect lower cost for techno polymer coming from recycling.

Then **car dismantler** will have business opportunities to sell at higher price techno-polymer to the recyclers but they will have to invest in technical and human resources to properly recover the techno polymers.

Scrap dealers will clearly lose business but **Logistics providers** will increase their business due to an increase of transportation needs of reverse logistics.

Main actors' side-effects table for Techno-polymer (B2B)

Actors	Pros	Cons (Side-effects)
Tier 1 suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase of the product portfolio with product coming from recycling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less business and more competition for tiers 1 supplier due to lower cost of components made from recycling techno polymers.
Raw material suppliers		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less revenues, less raw material sold thanks to techno polymer recycling business
OEM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase the product portfolio: new car/Vehicles with Circular Economy purpose Could expect lower cost for techno polymer coming from recycling 	
Car workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase the product portfolio: new car/Vehicles with Circular Economy purpose Could expect lower cost for techno polymer coming from recycling 	
Car Dismantlers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business opportunities to sale at higher price techno polymer to the recyclers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investment in new technologies Lack of knowledge
Recyclers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Big opportunities Waste reduction No deficit of material quality 	
Polymer scrap dealers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> May enter the recycling business 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Loss of business
Logistics providers: carriers & transporters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More business due to increase transportation needs of reverse logistics 	

Table 4. Main actors' side-effects table for Techno-polymer (B2B)

4 CONCLUSION

The deliverable has been focused on the side-effects generated for each Re-use value chains (Battery, Metal and Techno-polymer) as well as shared mobility services B2C. The methodology for the identification of drawbacks and side effects consisted in the following steps:

1) first identification of drawbacks and side effects by a restricted group of partners, that combined their multi-disciplinary knowledge to identify drawbacks. In particular, the activity was led by the partner Avicenne that, by operating as a consulting company in the global market of batteries, could provide its wide business and marketing intelligence knowledge. CNR contributed in this phase by proposing and introducing a model to exhaustively identify and represent interlinked variables. Such a model consisted in two main instruments:

- Tables for the systematic identification of pros and cons of each business scenario for all involved actors
- Map of interlinked variables determining drawbacks and interrelations. Variables in the maps can be identified considering the pros and cons that emerged in the previous tables.

Then a workshop regarding the 4th General Assembly with consortium partners has been conducted. During the workshop three groups were created, where each group focused on a table with main actors (stakeholders) for each value chain to analytically analyse the drawbacks. Indeed, the table of each value chain actors has been completed based on different consequences that will be arisen from each reuse Business Model Canvas from T2.1 and T2.2. To do so, contributed partners to each table had time to methodically define side-effects and positive impacts on the existing market players as well as on new proposed businesses.

The major side effects of the project could be summarized as follow: less business for

- OEM: less car sold,
- Battery pack suppliers and all the battery supply chain (Battery re-use decrease the need of new batteries),
- Metal part suppliers and metal works, but on a long-term basis, as the quality of remanufacturing product decrease, the impact is limited
- Techno polymer raw material suppliers; on a long-term basis the impact could be huge as the techno-polymer could be recycled without any lost in performances forever.

On the other hand, circular economy in the EV car sharing services will bring major positive impacts:

- Environmental: less CO₂ consumption thanks to EV but also thanks to less battery production and metal part remanufacturing,
- Global cost decrease at all the level of the value-chain: 2nd life battery, remanufacturing metal parts and recycled techno-polymer will be cheaper; EV made with those recycled and remanufactured products will be cheaper,
- Creation of new business: battery pack dismantling, testing and remanufacturing, metal part remanufacturing, techno-polymer recycling, additional business for car dismantler, new logistical business and model thanks to the ICT Platform and the Smart Mobile Modules.

This Task will provide inputs for the development of economic models that can be used for the assessment of socio-economic impacts of new circular business models in T2.4: "Socio-economic simulation of new services and business models".

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